

THE ROLE OF PHONETIC GAMES IN THE FORMATION OF PHONETIC SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: Knowledge of a foreign language is no longer a fashion, but a necessity in a developing modern society. Consequently, foreign languages have long been an integral part of the initial stage of school education. In primary school, the current goal of education is to develop all elements of communicative competence, in which language skills play an important role. Language skills play an important role in development. One of the most difficult and important tasks for teachers in the development of communicative competence, in which language skills play an important role. The goal is to master the correct English pronunciation, and learning foreign languages should begin with learning the phonological system of the language. After all, the correct pronunciation of sounds contributes to both correct pronunciation and is no less important for understanding what has been said than for conveying meaning. Phonetics, being one of the main sections of learning a foreign language, is more effective in practice. Phonetics, as one of the main sections of learning a foreign language, is more effective in practice. Thus, phonetic games are one of the most effective ways to consolidate pronounce skills. For example, the pedagogical phenomenon of student play has been interpreted in the works of A.S. Makarenko, V.A.Sukhomlinsky, D.B. Elkonin, etc. Sukhomlinsky, D.B.Elkonin and others; K.D. Ushinsky, J. Serre, K.Bhalla considered the game as a manifestation of imagination and fantasy, A.-I. Sikorsky and J. Dewey associated the game with the development of thinking. L.A. Verbitskaya, N.-S. Trubetskoy, L.V. Shcherba, R.O. Jacobson, E.Fischer-Jergensen, D.B. Fry, M.-S. took part in the development of phonetics. Templin, B.L.Wellman, R.H.Weir, etc.

Keywords: acoustic approach, articulatory approach, differentiated approach, game, interference, skill, auditory-pronunciation skills, speech hearing, rhythmic-intonation skills, auditory attention, phonemic hearing, phonetics, phonetic hearing, phonetic skills.

РОЛЬ ФОНЕТИЧЕСКИХ ИГР В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ФОНЕТИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация: Знание иностранного языка - это уже не мода, а необходимость в развивающемся современном обществе. Следовательно, иностранные языки уже давно стали неотъемлемой частью начального этапа школьного образования. В начальной школе текущей целью образования является развитие всех элементов коммуникативной компетенции, в которой языковые навыки играют важную роль. Языковые навыки играют важную роль в развитии. Одна из самых сложных и важных задач для учителей в развитии коммуникативной компетентности, в которой языковые навыки играют важную роль. Цель состоит в том, чтобы овладеть правильным английским произношением, и изучение иностранных языков должно начинаться с изучения фонологической системы языка. В конце концов, правильное произношение звуков способствует как правильному произношению, так и не менее важно для понимания сказанного, чем для передачи смысла. Фонетика, являясь одним из основных разделов изучения иностранного языка, более эффективна на практике. Фонетика, как один из основных разделов изучения иностранного языка, более эффективна на практике. Таким образом, фонетические игры являются одним

из наиболее эффективных способов закрепления навыков произношения. Например, педагогический феномен студенческой игры был осмыслен в работах А.С. Макаренко, В.А.Сухомлинского, Д.Б. Эльконина и др. Сухомлинский, Д.Б.Эльконин и другие; К.Д. Ушинский, Ж. Серр, К.Бхалла рассматривали игру как проявление воображения и фантазии, А.-И. Сикорский и Дж. Дьюи связывали игру с развитием мышления. Л.А. Вербицкая, Н.-С. Трубецкой, Л.В. Щерба, Р.О. Якобсон, Э.Фишер-Йергенсен, Д.Б. Фрай, М.-С. принимал участие в развитии фонетики. Темплин, Б.Л.Уэллман, Р.Х.Вейр и др.

Ключевые слова: акустический подход, артикуляционный подход, дифференцированный подход, игра, интерференция, навык, навыки слухопроизношения, речевой слух, ритмико-интонационные навыки, слуховое внимание, фонематический слух, фонетика, фонетический слух, фонетические навыки.

INTRODUCTION

A foreign language, unlike other subjects, is both a goal and a means of learning. The success of training depends on the individual psychological and professional characteristics of the teacher's personality, on the personality of the student, his interests and attitude to study. The basics of good pronunciation of sounds, rhythmically and intonationally correct speech design and understanding of speech by ear should be laid at the initial stage of learning a foreign language. When forming phonetic skills, learning brings the greatest effect in games, because the game activates mental activity allows you to make the learning process more attractive and interesting, and the difficulties that arise during learning are overcome with the greatest success and ease. As an example, we can quote V.A. Sukhomlinsky: "There is no full-fledged mental development without a game, and there can be no full-fledged mental development. The game is a spark that ignites a spark of inquisitiveness and curiosity" [3, p. 33].

There are a huge number of games aimed at achieving certain goals in the methodology of teaching a foreign language, so here the question arises: what is a phonetic game and what is it aimed at?

The goals pursued by the phonetic game:

- Set or correct the correct pronunciation;
- train students in pronunciation of English words in isolation, in words and phrases;
- practice intonation;
- teach students to read aloud loudly and clearly [2].

But the main purpose of using phonetic games in English lessons is the consolidation and improvement of pronunciation skills, developing auditory attention and memory, the ability to hear and differentiate sounds by longitude and brevity, to hear interdental sounds [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thus, we can formulate the following definition:

Phonetic game is a game aimed at consolidating or improving phonetic skills, contributing to the correct pronunciation of sounds in the speech stream, the development of auditory attention and memory, the ability to hear and differentiate sounds, both in isolation and in the speech stream, as well as intonation and rhythmically correct speech design.

Phonetic games are divided into the following subgroups:

- Games for the development of phonemic hearing.

They contribute to the correct perception of English phonetics, help to cope with the problem of the dissimilarity of languages, because when learning English, a student faces such a problem as the absence of similar phonemes in his native language.

- Games for the development of sound production skills.

The correct sound pronunciation is understood as the pure pronunciation of each sound of speech by children and the mastery of the laws of the combination of these sounds in syllables and words. There are two ways to master this complex process: informational (imitation of the speech of people around you) and formal (special training). This type of games helps to develop the skills of correct pronunciation of English sounds according to the standards of English speech. It is believed that the development of this skill is the most difficult, but very important.

- Game techniques in teaching transcription.

Learning transcription is an integral part of learning English, because knowledge of transcription will allow the child to start working with a dictionary earlier, to find the correct pronunciation of words.

- Game techniques in teaching intonation.
- Game techniques for training especially pronunciation skills.

Having defined the goals and role of phonetic games in the process of forming phonetic skills at the initial stage of learning a foreign language, we can distinguish their functions:

The training function is the formation of phonetic skills (auditory-pronouncing and rhythmic-intonation).

The educational function consists in the education of such qualities as teamwork, respect for partners or rivals in the game, mutual assistance.

The developing function contributes to the development of such mental cognitive processes as thinking, memory, perception and attention, and the disclosure of such personal qualities as mobility, perseverance, stress resistance, etc. Develops strong-willed qualities and the experience of various emotions.

The entertainment function is to create a favorable atmosphere in the classroom, which makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting, exciting and relaxed.

The communicative function is to create a situation of foreign language communication, contributing to the emergence of new emotional and communicative relationships.

The psychological function is to remove psychological difficulties (barriers).

The motor-speech function consists in the simultaneous operation of motor and speech activity. For example, when a student reads a poem and at the same time performs movements.

The game is used as a means of clarity and as an exercise. Educational games can be characterized by educational goals and objectives, the form of conduct, the way of organization, the degree of complexity, the quantitative composition of students. It is worth remembering that games are not an end in themselves, but a means of activating vocabulary, grammar, work on pronunciation, reading, writing and oral speech [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial stage of training is a favorable period for the formation of correct pronunciation, which undoubtedly includes observing pauses, correct intonation, articulation, stress. Practiced pronunciation skills lead to the implementation of speaking, auditory skills allow you to differentiate sounds (by longitude / brevity, etc.), rhythmic-intonation skills allow you to learn rhythm, stress, intonation. All this contributes to the functioning of students' oral speech. The task of mastering foreign pronunciation is to adapt the psychophysiological mechanisms of perception

and speech according to the phonetic system of the language being studied by correcting existing or developing additional auditory-pronunciation skills. An equally important role the potential abilities of the child to perceive speech by ear and the mobility of articulation organs play [5].

Using phonetic games in foreign language lessons, we must take into account their purpose. So, phonetic games are divided into two types: some are aimed at preventing / preventing errors, and others at correcting / correcting errors. The difficulty of working with phonetic games lies in the fact that even the most complex sounds and sound combinations can occur from the very first lessons, so it is impossible to simplify the language material, so that the material worked out in the classroom does not immediately turn into spontaneous speech.

Phonetic games are characterized by such a principle of conducting, as from simple to complex, either the game is associated with the words entered the classroom, or they are needed to correct the most gross mistakes. During the phonetic game, at first there is some important difference in sound combinations for assimilation, after that the difference in pronunciation is associated with the difference in meaning. Each time, the difference in meaning is associated with the difference in sound, which is clearly visible to the students.

It is worth noting that the phonetic aspect of teaching foreign language speech to children is considered the most difficult for younger schoolchildren to assimilate.

At the initial stage of learning a foreign language, phonetic games are used as illustrations and exercises for practicing the most difficult sounds for pronunciation, intonation or as phonetic charging. The implementation of phonetic games takes place at the level of words, sentences, rhymes, tongue twisters, poems, songs, since the experience gained in games of this type can be used by students in the future in foreign language classes.

Phonetic games in which rhyming takes place are appropriate when introducing a new phonetic phenomenon, when performing exercises to consolidate new phonetic material and when repeating it, as well as during phonetic exercises, but at the initial stage, rhyming can also be used to process the sound side of speech. Tongue twisters used in a foreign language lesson will help the teacher to work out the pronunciation of individual consonants in a relaxed playful way, they are the best means of achieving clarity of speech at any pace [5].

Phonetic games used at the initial stage (primary school) of learning include [2]:

- simulation games;
- puzzle games;
- games-competitions;
- playing with objects;
- lotto games with sounds;
- mindfulness games.

So, games include a variety of forms of conducting, and most importantly, facilitate the development of the phonetic side of speech, which is the most difficult component of the language to assimilate. The formation of phonetic skills is possible with the systematic use of phonetic games.

The formation and improvement of phonetic skills of primary school students at the initial stage of learning a foreign language in a playful way undoubtedly contributes to a strong and effective assimilation of the phonetic system of the language. Moreover, the game increases the child's interest in learning a foreign language, makes the learning process exciting and relaxed, because, despite the fact that learning acquires a leading importance in primary school age, the need for play, the desire to move forward, to get positive emotions remains.

CONCLUSIONS

The importance of the formation of phonetic skills in primary school age is explained by the psychophysiological characteristics of children, when there is an active development of cognitive processes, such as thinking, imagination, attention, perception, memory, in particular, long-term.

The systematic use of phonetic games in foreign language lessons contributes to the effective formation and improvement of phonetic skills in younger schoolchildren at the initial stage of learning a foreign language in a primary school.

REFERENCES:

1. Kiseleva E. Yu., Gorbunova T. S. Phonetic games and exercises at the initial stage of learning Russian as a foreign language and English languages: scientific. an article on the specialty "Linguistics". – 2014. – 5 p.
2. Solovova E.N. Methods of teaching foreign languages: An advanced course of lectures / E.N. Solovova. – M.: AST, 2010. – 272 p.
3. Sukhomlinsky, V.A. I give my heart to children. - Minsk: Narodnaya asveta, 1988. – 288 p.
4. The specifics of the initial stage of FL training. – 2015. – [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://goo.gl/ZKZ0fy> (date of address: 04/15/16).
5. Tretyak O.V. Phonetic games in English lessons: educational method. manual / O.V. Tretyak. – Orenburg, 2013.